

Dystocia Due to Ventral Abdominal Wall Defective Kitten in a 4 -Years-Old Queen: A Case Report

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Submission: 14th November, 2025; Accepted: 25nd December, 2025; Published: 30th December, 2025

Abstract

Dystocia in queens may arise from maternal or fetal causes, with most parturition completed within a few hours. A 4-year-old queen weighing 3 kg was presented to Gwale Veterinary Hospital, Kano, Kano State, after delivering two kittens and continuing to strain unsuccessfully for several hours. Clinical examination, revealed normal vital parameters and abdominal palpation confirmed the presence of another fetus within the uterus. An emergency caesarean section was performed, resulting in delivery of viable kitten. However, the ventral abdominal wall of the fetus failed to fuse, exposing the abdominal contents and the heart, displacing the organs from their normal anatomical position, which led to a congenital abnormality called ventral abdominal wall defect/Gastroschisis. The kitten died 35 minutes postpartum. This case highlight the rarity of gastroschisis as a cause of dystocia in feline species and underscores the importance of antenatal monitoring and timely obstetrical intervention to improve neonatal outcomes.

Keywords: Abdominal wall Defect; Gastroschisis; Kitten; Feline Queen.

1.0 Introduction

Dystocia is a prolonged or difficult parturition that requires manual or surgical intervention to assist the delivery of the fetus [1,2]. Usually due to either maternal causes (primary or secondary uterine inertia, inadequate pelvic size, uterine torsion, and cervical stenosis) or fetal causes (fetomaternal disproportion, fetal mal-disposition, fetal anomalies, and fetal death) [3]. Gestation in feline species is roughly 65 days in length and climax in three phases of labor [4,5,6]. The 1st stage is noticeable by advancing uterine contractions and cervical dilation, while stages 2 and 3 culminate at the delivery of the fetus and fetal membrane, respectively [7]. In queens, the total duration of labor is typically short, and all neonates are often born within 6 hours of the first kitten [8,5]. The interval between delivery times is uncertain, but about 95% of kittens are born within 100 minutes of each other [9,4]. In addition, interrupted labor does occur in queens during which the queen will pause

active stage 2 labor, then resume fetal expulsion, with no obvious detriment to either the dam or the remaining fetuses [1]. This is the opposite of dystocia, in which the normal advancement of labor is disrupted and the health of the dam and its fetus(es) may be endangered [8]. The following clinical signs are evidence of dystocia in queens (cats): prolonged gestation (>68–70 days), strong abdominal contractions for >30 minutes without a kitten, interruption between kittens >2–3 hours, foul vaginal discharge, depression, vocalization, retained kitten, uterine inertia and abnormal fetal position [3]. Gastroschisis or ventral abdominal wall defect is a rare congenital abnormality characterized by failure of the abdominal wall to fuse [10]. This defect results in the abdominal contents being seen uncovered, which eventually prevents the abdominal organs from returning to their normal anatomical position in the abdominal cavity [11]. There is a paucity of literature centering on feline dystocia, especially those caused by congenital defects

like Gastroschisis. Thus, this case report discussed one of the leading congenital abnormalities in human and ruminant neonates that rarely occur in feline species.

2.0 Case History

On 10th June, 2025, a queen weighing 3 kg was presented to Gwale Veterinary Hospital, Kano State, the owner reported that the queen had successfully delivered two (2) kittens but remained restless and continued to strain for several hours without delivering additional offspring. Obstetrical history revealed that the previous queening was successful without any difficulty. Upon clinical examination, all vital parameters were within the normal range. The queen was found to be lethargic, and abdominal palpation revealed the presence of another fetus within the uterus. Obstetrical assessment revealed a swollen and wet vulva.

The case was diagnosed based on history, physical and obstetrical examination and exploratory laparotomy. The following differentials were drawn: (1) Dystocia due to secondary uterine inertia, (2) Dystocia due to fetal monster (3) Dystocia due to fetal death, and (4) Dystocia due to severe congenital malformation (Diprosopus, Schistosomus reflexus, Gastroschisis, etc.), where gastroschisis was the most likely cause of the dystocia.

2.1 Management

A caesarean section was carried out to deliver the retained fetus. The surgical risk was good, the client was informed about the clinical findings and possible complications of the procedure, the client agreed, and signed the consent form. The queen was placed on dorsal recumbency, then surgical site was shaved and aseptically prepared using chlorhexidine gluconate, the queen was sedated using xylazine, surgical site was draped and a ventral midline incision was performed, the uterus was exteriorized, incision was made on the uterine horn containing the fetus, the kitten was successfully delivered and the fetus was viable as described in Plate 1. However, the surgical team noticed that the fetus ventral abdominal wall failed to fuse, exposing the visceral and the heart, displacing the organs from their normal anatomical position, which led to a congenital abnormality called ventral body wall defect/Gastroschisis as seen in Plate 2. The surgeon tried to replaced the organs back to their normal anatomical position but due to the negative pressure, the abdominal content remained

outside Plate 3. Unfortunately, the kitten died 35 minutes after it was delivered.

The uterus was sutured with chromic catgut size 2-0 using a cushion suture pattern; likewise, the musculature was sutured with the same material but using a simple continuous suture pattern. Subcutaneous tissue was sutured with chromic catgut using a subcuticular suture pattern, while the skin was sutured with silk size 2-0 using a Ford interlocking suture pattern.

2.2 Post Operation Management

A postoperative medication was instituted, where Meloxicam injection at 0.3mg/kg was administered subcutaneously once daily for 3 days, Ceftriaxone injection 10mg/kg was giving Intramuscular once daily for five days and B-complex injection at 5mg/kg once daily for 3 days was also administered intramuscular. Follow-up visit revealed that all drugs were administered accordingly, suture material was removed on the 12th day post-operation, and the queen recovered successfully Plate 4. The client was advised to provide an Elizabethan collar, to keep the wound area clean, and to monitor any possible complications that may arise. In addition, the client was also advised to keep the queen indoors and improve her diet.

Plate 1: Delivery of the Kitten Following Cesarean Section

Plate 2: Exposed Visceral Due to Failure of the Abdominal Wall to Fuse

Plate 3: Surgeon Trying to Replaced the Exposed Viscera Back

Plate 4: Queen After Suture has been Removed
 Bulletins of Natural and Applied Sciences(2025).3(2):8-12

3.0 Discussion

Management of dystocia in queen cat requires gentle approach, confidence, and a thorough physical examination before making any decision, because queen cats are nervous and elusive animal [12]. In this case cesarean section was performed to deliver the retained fetus, due to the prolonged ketten interval (7-8 hours) this is similar to the findings of Talukder *et al.* [13]. Dar *et al.* [14] reported that caesarean section is the best way with a high percentage of success for the treatment of dystocia in queens if done in the right procedures. However, the causes or origin of dystocia remained a challenge. Dystocia in cats is less common than in dogs, with a reported incidence of 3-6%, and occurs more frequently in purebred cats than in mixed-breed cats [13]. Other factors that may account for a breed variation in dystocia include litter size, body conformation, and body condition score (BCS). Litter size has been described to vary between breeds and to be significantly associated with dystocia [15]. In the current case the reason differ from the earlier mentioned causes, because here the principal cause was fetal congenital abnormality which is a rare occurrence in the queen cats. The problems with parturition in queens, which may affect normal delivery stated in previous studies, like ovariectomy [16], uterine prolapse [17], uterine torsion [18], and dystocia due to ectopic artery [19]. These difficulties may disregard free choices for treatment of dystocia and lean toward Caesarean section or ovariectomy choice [20]. Data from a study conducted by Ekstrand and Forsberg [21] revealed that dystocia due to maternal origin in queen cats is significantly higher in percentage if compared with the fetal origin. In addition, a high incidence of uterine inertia is considered to be the major cause of maternal dystocia in queens [7,20]. Birth defects, which are not uncommon in the offspring of a herd, are anomalies in the structure and/or function of a certain system of the organism or part of it [22]. Gastroschisis or omphalocele is one of those anomalies and has been reported in foals, dogs, pigs, buffaloes, calves, goats, dolphins, and sheep [11]. However, its cause remains unknown, although it is speculated that the condition is caused by a recessive genetic trait; it has not been confirmed as a hereditary anomaly [10]. In humans, gastroschisis or omphalocele is often associated with other anomalies, and, in addition to the intestine, other organs of the abdomen may be involved, which significantly increases mortality

[23]. The kitten in this report presented with open abdominal content due to the failure of the ventral abdominal wall to fuse; the abnormalities associated with this congenital defect have been under-reported in the literature, especially in kittens [24]. The case described herein demonstrates how such an abnormality delayed parturition and the clinical approach that led to early diagnosis and management of the condition.

4.0 Conclusion

Dystocia due to failure of the abdominal wall to fuse or Gastroschisis is common in humans and ruminant species. However, its occurrence in small animals, especially feline species, is rare and under-reported. Evidence-based shift from conservative obstetrical manipulation to immediate surgical resolution is a cardinal in managing cases of dystocia in queen cats. Veterinarians should emphasize the importance of antenatal monitoring of pregnant animals, especially at early and late gestation, this will aid in the early diagnosis, management and prevention of such conditions.

Acknowledgement

We acknowledged the efforts and assistance of the clinicians and technologists of the Gwale Veterinary Hospital, Kano.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

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